

Conference Abstract

From LTER to LTSER: The case of Ramat Hanadiv's Mountain Gazelle Population

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Abstract

The Israeli Mountain gazelle (*Gazella gazella*) is a large, attractive mammal, a "flagship species", and the wildlife species most identified with nature conservation in Israel's Mediterranean region. The species plays an important role in a variety of ecosystems, but its population has been declining in recent decades, mainly due to habitat loss, increased predation, illegal hunting and fragmentation of sub-populations in small areas. Consequently, the species is considered Endangered. Since the establishment of Ramat Hanadiv's LTER site and monitoring program in 2003, gazelles have been continuously monitored, with the aim of tracking population dynamics and demographic changes over time. Data is collected throughout the year by direct observations along a fixed transect which covers large parts of the park and represents a variety of factors which potentially affect gazelle distribution, e.g., slope, vegetation structure, cattle grazing regime, and proximity to trails. The results show a recovery of the gazelle population between 2012–2015, followed by relative population stability. However, since 2018 a marked decline in gazelle numbers has been recorded.

To enhance the recovery of the gazelle population, several efforts and actions were carried out simultaneously. An in-depth study was launched to characterize the factors limiting the population, which pointed to predation as a main factor, particularly by jackals (*Canis aureus*), which have proliferated due to increased availability of anthropogenic food; several gazelles from breeding programs were released in the park, and a regional campaign was initiated, together with environmental organizations and support from the

community, to promote a wide ecological corridor between Ramat Hanadiv and neighboring protected areas and increase the connectivity between the local and other gazelle populations. Recently, ongoing mapping and monitoring of anthropogenic food sources was also initiated, aiming to reduce the availability of food for jackals, alongside with efforts to raise awareness of the issue and harness farmers and the authorities in the region to find sustainable solutions to this problem.

These concerted efforts have facilitated the transformation of Ramat Hanadiv from an LTER site into a socio-ecological platform (LTSER) within the European network, underscoring the integration of ecological research with community engagement in conservation practices.

Keywords

Mountain gazelle, Mediterranean Nature Park, Jackals, LTSER, monitoring, Israel

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.